

ConCur: Knowledge Graph Construction and Curation

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Abstract

Knowledge Graphs (KGs), which are often understood to include both graph structured data composed of relational facts and ontological knowledge, have become increasingly popular for data management, knowledge representation and artificial intelligence. Such KGs often use RDF to represent facts and RDF Schema plus the Web Ontology Language (OWL) to represent ontologies. The project ConCur, hosted in University of Oxford, explores innovative theories and methods across various aspects for automating KG construction and curation, with a focus on ontology embedding, alignment, population and completion using both semantic technologies and machine learning methods, including (large) language models. The project has published a series of papers in Computer Science conferences and journals that report the developed methods, their experimental results and empirical studies; it has also constructed and released open-source data resources and system implementations that can benefit research and applications in both academia and industry. This report will summarize the project's research results and briefly introduce other project details including team members and industry partners.

Keywords

Knowledge Graph Construction, Ontology Engineering, Semantic Embedding, Language Model

1. Project information

- Project short name/acronym: ConCur
- Project full name: Knowledge Graph Construction and Curation
- Project website link: <https://www.cs.ox.ac.uk/isg/projects/ConCur/>
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2. Project summary

Knowledge Graphs (KGs) have become an increasingly popular approach for knowledge representation and data management. The definition of a KG varies across research communities. In some cases, a KG seen as a collection of relational facts represented as RDF triples, and in others it can be a simple taxonomy, such as eBay's product categories. However, among Semantic Web researchers, it is also

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sometimes understood to include both facts and ontological schemas represented using RDF Schema and OWL ontologies grounded in Description Logic. ConCur considers all the above definitions of KGs, and aims to investigate theories, methods, systems and resources for KG construction and curation, involving a broad range of topics including knowledge extraction from data, entity alignment and knowledge integration, knowledge completion and canonicalization, semantic embedding for neural-symbolic knowledge representation and reasoning. Since the project started in December 2021 it has contributed novel research in all these topics. Its core contributions can be summarized as follow:

- Novel ontology alignment methods and resources, including BERTMap [1] and BERTSubs [2] which fine-tune pre-trained language models (PLMs) for concept mapping with, respectively, equivalence and subsumption relationships; Large Language Model (LLM) prompts for concept equivalence mapping [3]; and Bio-ML [4] which includes new datasets and metrics for efficiently and effectively evaluating machine learning-based ontology alignment systems.
- A systematic review of the ontology embedding literature [5], and novel ontology embedding methods including Box²EL [6] that preserves the semantics of the Description Logic \mathcal{EL}^{++} via complex geometric modeling, and HiT [7] that encodes concepts with their hierarchy structure and textual labels incorporated by continuous training of PLMs.
- Novel ontology completion methods such as BLINKOut [8] for detecting new medical concepts from text and [9] for placing such new concepts in biomedical ontologies, both employing fine-tuning of PLMs with contrastive learning strategies. They also include ICON [10] – a system that can detect implicit concepts in e-commerce taxonomies, generate suitable names and place them appropriately in the taxonomy using PLM-based subsumption prediction and optimized search over tree-like graphs.

Additionally, ConCur has also studied other relevant topics combining natural language processing, language models and OWL ontologies, including verbalization of complex concepts and logical expressions, and utilizing such verbalization for probing the knowledge and reasoning capabilities of language models (i.e., OntoLAMA) [11] and for retrieving axioms that can be aligned with natural language input [12]. The project team also collaborates with external partners such as Tencent and Zhejiang University for research on KGs of relational facts, including entity alignment (e.g., [13, 14, 15]) and KG completion, either with or without new entities/relations (e.g., [16, 17]).

3. Project available results

ConCur releases all the codes and datasets for experiments of each study, with the repository link attached in the relevant paper; it has also developed the following system implementation and data resources:

- DeepOnto¹ is a Python library aimed at enabling the application of language models and other deep learning techniques in ontology engineering [18]. It adopts JPyype² to utilise the existing Java OWL API³ for implementing Python APIs for ontology processing, covering not only basic operations such as loading, editing and saving, but also some advanced and commonly used features, such as axiom normalization, taxonomy (concept hierarchy) extraction, projection (transforming the axioms into a multi-relation graph), and verbalisation (describing complex concepts and logical expression in natural language text). Based on these features, DeepOnto has implemented BERTMap, BERTSubs, OntoLAMA, and the Bio-ML data construction and evaluation toolkits, and is under further extension. Note that many other studies (e.g., [9, 12]) in this project also adopt DeepOnto for implementing their experiment codes.

¹Github repository: <https://github.com/KRR-Oxford/DeepOnto>
Documents: <https://krr-oxford.github.io/DeepOnto/>

²<https://jpyype.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

³<https://owlapi.sourceforge.net/>

- The Bio-ML track of the Ontology Alignment Evaluation Initiative (OAEI)⁴ which has been hosted since 2022. It includes not only 5 datasets (ontology pairs) with ground truth mappings of both concept equivalence and concept subsumption that are constructed with existing annotations and ontology pruning techniques, but also a new local evaluation protocol with ranking-based metrics that is more efficient for evaluating machine learning-based systems, as well as traditional assessment over final output mappings with metrics of Precision and Recall. Up to 2024, 20 ontology alignment systems/methods have been evaluated in Bio-ML, with results reported.

4. Relevance to ESWC conference

There are many reasons that make us believe that this project is suitable to the conference's project networking track. Here are some of the more important ones: (1) The research topics and all the studies conducted fully fall into the scope of ESWC. (2) The project has led to significant impact in different communities including the Semantic Web, with over 20 publications in high-quality conferences and journals, and some useful and accessible resources (e.g., DeepOnto has over 600 downloads via PyPi in March 2025 according to PyPI Stats⁵ and got an outstanding resource award from the OpenKG community in 2024). (3) The project falls into the type of "Concluding projects" – it ends in the month before ESWC 2025. (4) Three (previous) team members of the project – Dr. Jiaoyan Chen, Dr. Hang Dong and Dr. Jieying Chen – have become early-stage faculty in European universities, and are keen to participate new collaborative projects. In particular, Jiaoyan Chen has ensured the participation of ESWC 2025, including all the activities of project network.

5. Value brought by the project to ESWC participants

This project will bring the following to the ESWC participants: (1) methodologies, and their empirical studies and evaluation results for different aspects of KG construction and curation; (2) the DeepOnto library and other open-source codes of the aforementioned studies; (3) datasets and evaluation resources for ontology alignment (besides the Bio-ML resources for ontology alignment, we have also contributed some new resources for the other studies, such as a new biomedical dataset for evaluating concept discovery from text and concept placement in ontologies, which got the best resource award (runner-up) in CIKM 2023 [19], a new and more comprehensive ontology completion testing set for evaluating embedding methods [6], and a new dataset for text and OWL axiom alignment [12]).

6. Value gained by the project from ESWC participation

Through participating in the project networking activities of ESWC, the project as well as all its team members will definitely benefit a lot in many aspects, especially the following: (1) It will help to disseminate the project's output, including methods, resources and codes, significantly accelerating their impact among Semantic Web researchers, companies and beyond. (2) ESWC attendees will likely give constructive feedback which will not only improve the project's output, but also benefit the team members' future research and career development. (3) The project's team members, especially those who participate ESWC 2025 onsite, will have promising opportunities for building research collaborations and participating in collaborative projects across universities in Europe.

Acknowledgments

The following members directly contributed to the project: Ian Horrocks who is the PI, Jiaoyan Chen who is a Research Co-Investigator, Yuan He who participated the project during his whole PhD career

⁴<https://krr-oxford.github.io/OAEI-Bio-ML/>

⁵<https://pypistats.org/packages/deeponeto>

and is now a postdoctoral researcher on the project, Jingchuan Shi who participated as a PhD student, Hang Dong and Jieying Chen who contributed as postdoctoral researchers. The industrial coordinators, including Denvar Antonyrajah, Brahmananda Sapkota, Carlo Allocca and Taehun Kim from Samsung, Zhe Wu from eBay, and Xi Chen from Tencent, also participated in the project. They played a critical role in building the collaborations. Crucially, the project was directly funded by SRUK and eBay as well as by EPSRC.

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